

Epistatic interactions among co-inherited malaria-protective red blood cell polymorphisms and their effects across the infection-to-mortality spectrum in endemic regions: a systematic review

George Paasi, Paul Ongodia, Nancy Malaika, Denis Amorut

Citation

George Paasi, Paul Ongodia, Nancy Malaika, Denis Amorut. Epistatic interactions among co-inherited malaria-protective red blood cell polymorphisms and their effects across the infection-to-mortality spectrum in endemic regions: a systematic review. PROSPERO 2025 CRD420251088652. Available from <https://www.crd.york.ac.uk/PROSPERO/view/CRD420251088652>.

REVIEW TITLE AND BASIC DETAILS

Review title

Epistatic interactions among co-inherited malaria-protective red blood cell polymorphisms and their effects across the infection-to-mortality spectrum in endemic regions: a systematic review

Condition or domain being studied

The review specifically explores epistatic interactions (gene-gene interactions) among polymorphisms including sickle-cell trait (HbAS), α^+ -thalassemia, glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase deficiency (G6PD deficiency), and complement receptor 1 (CR1), among others, assessing how these interactions alter malaria risk across various clinical manifestations in malaria-endemic settings.

Rationale for the review

This systematic review addresses a crucial gap in understanding malaria susceptibility by comprehensively evaluating how epistatic interactions (gene-gene interactions) among co-inherited malaria-protective red blood cell polymorphisms affect disease outcomes. While numerous studies have identified individual erythrocyte variants such as sickle-cell trait (HbAS), α^+ -thalassemia, glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase deficiency (G6PD), and complement receptor-1 (CR1) as protective against *Plasmodium falciparum* malaria, the clinical implications of their combined inheritance remain unclear. Epistasis could lead to additive, synergistic, or antagonistic effects, altering malaria risk differently from expectations based solely on single polymorphisms. Despite widespread co-occurrence of these polymorphisms in malaria-endemic

populations, there has been no systematic synthesis of evidence on their interactions. Understanding how these interactions influence malaria susceptibility, clinical severity, and outcomes is vital for several reasons. First, it can significantly enhance the accuracy of genetic risk prediction models used for identifying vulnerable populations. Second, improved characterization of these interactions could inform personalized malaria interventions, including chemoprevention and vaccination strategies tailored to genetic backgrounds. Third, evidence from this review could refine current evolutionary models explaining why certain malaria-protective alleles persist at intermediate frequencies within populations. By synthesising existing epidemiological evidence, this review will provide the first comprehensive assessment of how multilocus genetic interactions influence malaria susceptibility and disease severity, bridging a major knowledge gap and guiding future research directions in malaria genetics, epidemiology, and public health planning.

Review objectives

To characterise the epistatic interactions among co-inherited malaria-protective RBC polymorphisms and determine how these interactions modify malaria risk across the infection-to-mortality continuum in endemic populations.

Keywords

Malaria; Epistasis ; Genetic polymorphisms; Red blood cells; Genetic susceptibility; Plasmodium falciparum; Coinheritance

Country

Uganda

ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

Population

Included

Studies involving humans of any age residing in Plasmodium falciparum malaria-endemic regions in Africa, Asia, or Oceania, investigating malaria outcomes related to co-inherited red blood cell genetic polymorphisms.

Excluded

Studies involving non-endemic populations, travellers, animal studies, or in-vitro experiments without human participants.

Intervention(s) or exposure(s)

Included

Included studies must specifically investigate the co-inheritance of at least two malaria-protective erythrocyte polymorphisms such as sickle-cell trait (HbAS), α^+ -thalassaemia, glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD) deficiency, complement receptor-1 (CR1), haptoglobin (Hp2-1), or PIEZO1.

Excluded

Studies focusing solely on single-locus polymorphisms, immune genes, or drug-metabolism genes not related to malaria-protective red blood cell polymorphisms.

Comparator(s) or control(s)

Included

The review includes studies comparing individuals carrying multiple malaria-protective red blood cell polymorphisms with individuals carrying single polymorphisms or wild-type genotypes.

Excluded

Studies lacking a clearly defined comparator group (either single polymorphism carriers or wild-type individuals) for assessing epistatic interactions.

Study design

Both randomized and nonrandomized study types will be included.

Included

Eligible studies include observational designs such as cohort, case-control, and cross-sectional studies that report genotype-by-outcome data on malaria-related endpoints (e.g., parasite density, uncomplicated malaria, severe malaria, or malaria-attributable mortality) in relation to co-inherited red blood cell polymorphisms. Studies with clearly defined exposure and comparator groups and sufficient outcome data for epistatic analysis will be included. Randomised studies will be included only if they meet these criteria.

Excluded

In-vitro or animal studies, conference abstracts without full methods, reviews, editorials, and studies reporting only single-locus associations without testing for genetic interaction will be excluded.

Context

Malaria continues to exert a high disease burden across many endemic regions, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa and parts of Asia and Oceania. Decades of research have shown that certain red blood cell (RBC) polymorphisms, such as sickle-cell trait (HbAS), α^+ -thalassemia, and glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD) deficiency, confer protection against *Plasmodium falciparum* infection and its severe complications. These polymorphisms have been naturally selected over generations due to their survival advantage in malaria-endemic environments. However, individuals in these populations often inherit multiple protective polymorphisms together, raising important questions about how these alleles interact to modify disease risk. The interplay between protective variants referred to as epistasis can be additive, synergistic, or antagonistic, potentially amplifying or nullifying their individual benefits. Despite its biological plausibility and clinical relevance, epistasis remains underexplored in the malaria literature, and no prior systematic review has synthesised this evidence across settings and outcome domains. Understanding these gene-gene interactions is essential for improving genetic risk prediction, refining vaccine and chemoprevention trial stratification, and advancing evolutionary models of host-pathogen dynamics. This review therefore aims to fill a major knowledge gap by collating and evaluating studies that examine the co-inheritance of malaria-protective RBC polymorphisms in human populations. The findings will support a shift from single-locus thinking to integrated genomic approaches in malaria research, with implications for both personalised medicine and public health policy in high-burden regions.

TIMELINE OF THE REVIEW

Date of first submission to PROSPERO

06 July 2025

Review timeline

Start date: 6 July 2025. End date: 24 September 2025.

Date of registration in PROSPERO

07 July 2025

AVAILABILITY OF FULL PROTOCOL

Availability of full protocol

A full protocol has been written and uploaded to PROSPERO. The protocol may be accessed through this link

<https://www.crd.york.ac.uk/PROSPEROFILES/c1a940932d4fbced254cb4fc6d9f0516.pdf>.

SEARCHING AND SCREENING

Search for unpublished studies

Both published and unpublished studies will be sought.

Main bibliographic databases that will be searched

The main databases to be searched are *CENTRAL - Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials*, *CINAHL - Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature*, *Embase - Embase via Ovid*, *MEDLINE*, *PsycInfo*, *PubMed* and *Scopus*.

Other important or specialist databases that will be searched

Web of science

Search language restrictions

There are no language restrictions.

Search date restrictions

There are no search date restrictions.

Other methods of identifying studies

Other studies will be identified by: *contacting authors or experts, looking through all the articles that cite the papers included in the review ("snowballing"), reference list checking, searching conference proceedings, searching dissertation and thesis databases and searching trial or study registers.*

Link to search strategy

A full search strategy has been uploaded to PROSPERO. The PDF may be accessed through this link

<https://www.crd.york.ac.uk/PROSPEROFILES/a76fcb86abafc7b8b8b88f555d9d7a96.pdf>.

Selection process

Studies will be screened independently by at least two people (or person/machine combination) with a process to resolve differences.

Other relevant information about searching and screening

In addition to database searches, we will review the reference lists of all included studies and relevant reviews to identify any eligible articles missed in the primary search. Where full texts

are not readily available, authors will be contacted directly. The screening process will be piloted on a random sample of titles and abstracts to ensure consistency in applying inclusion criteria. Disagreements during screening or full-text review will be resolved through consensus or by involving a third reviewer. A PRISMA 2020 flow diagram will document the selection process. If necessary, grey literature sources and preprints will also be considered to minimize publication bias.

DATA COLLECTION PROCESS

Data extraction from published articles and reports

Data will be extracted independently by at least two people (or person/machine combination) with a process to resolve differences.

Authors will be asked to provide any required data not available in published reports.

Study risk of bias or quality assessment

Risk of bias will be assessed using: *Newcastle-Ottawa*

Data will be assessed independently by at least two people (or person/machine combination) with a process to resolve differences.

Additional information will be sought from study investigators if required information is unclear or unavailable in the study publications/reports.

Reporting bias assessment

Funnel plots and Egger's test will be used to assess small-study effects where ≥ 10 studies are included in a meta-analysis. We will also evaluate selective outcome reporting through comparison with study protocols or trial registries where available.

Certainty assessment

The certainty of evidence will be assessed using the GRADE (Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation) approach. This will consider five domains: risk of bias, inconsistency, indirectness, imprecision, and publication bias. Evidence will be rated as high, moderate, low, or very low certainty for each primary and secondary outcome. Summary of findings tables will be generated using GRADE to clearly present the strength of evidence. For outcomes not amenable to meta-analysis, GRADE criteria will still be applied to the best available narrative synthesis.

OUTCOMES TO BE ANALYSED

Main outcomes

The primary outcomes of interest in this review include the interaction effects of co-inherited malaria-protective red blood cell polymorphisms on key malaria endpoints. Specifically, these are: (1) incidence or odds of malaria infection (both uncomplicated and severe forms); (2) malaria parasite density as a continuous or stratified outcome; and (3) malaria-related mortality.

Additional outcomes

In addition to the primary outcomes of malaria infection, parasitaemia levels, and clinical disease (uncomplicated or severe malaria), this review will examine whether co-inheritance of malaria-protective red blood cell polymorphisms results in additive, synergistic, antagonistic, or

neutral effects on these outcomes. Specifically, we will assess the direction and magnitude of interaction effects between polymorphisms when jointly inherited, comparing genotype combinations to appropriate reference genotypes such as wild-type (HbAA, normal G6PD, etc.).

PLANNED DATA SYNTHESIS

Strategy for data synthesis

Formal synthesis is planned using meta-analytical techniques where sufficient homogeneity exists in study design, exposure definitions, and outcome measures. We will pool effect estimates for each co-inherited genotype pair separately, stratifying by outcome type (infection, parasitaemia, uncomplicated malaria, severe malaria) and study design (case-control, cohort, or cross-sectional). Random-effects models will be used to account for anticipated heterogeneity across populations and settings. We will prioritise extraction of interaction measures (e.g. ratio of odds ratios or additive interaction metrics) reported by primary studies. Where individual interaction estimates are unavailable, we will compare pooled effects of combined genotypes against effects of single polymorphisms and reference genotypes to infer potential interaction direction and magnitude.

Where meta-analysis is not appropriate due to methodological, statistical, or clinical heterogeneity, data will be synthesised narratively following the SWiM (Synthesis Without Meta-analysis) framework. This will involve structured tabulation, grouping by polymorphism combinations and outcome domains, and summarising findings by study design, geographic region, and malaria transmission intensity.

All syntheses will be stratified by age group and endemicity level where possible. Sensitivity analyses will be conducted excluding studies at high risk of bias. We will use forest plots, effect direction plots, and harvest plots to visualise findings. The possibility of publication bias will be explored where ≥ 10 studies are available for any outcome, using funnel plots and Egger's test. All analyses will be performed using R.

CURRENT REVIEW STAGE

Stage of the review at this submission

Review stage	Started	Completed
Pilot work		
Formal searching/study identification		
Screening search results against inclusion criteria		
Data extraction or receipt of IPD		
Risk of bias/quality assessment		
Data synthesis		

Review status

The review is currently planned or ongoing.

Publication of review results

Results of the review will be published in English.

REVIEW AFFILIATION, FUNDING AND PEER REVIEW

Review team members

Dr George Paasi (review guarantor and contact) Mbale clinical research institute. Uganda.

No conflict of interest declared.

Dr Paul Ongodia. Mbale Clinical Research Institute (MCRI). Uganda.

No conflict of interest declared.

Dr Nancy Malaika. Makerere University, college of Health sciences, School of medicine, Department of Paediatric and Child Health.. Uganda.

No conflict of interest declared.

Mr Denis Amorut. Mbale Clinical Research Institute (MCRI). Uganda.

No conflict of interest declared.

Named contact

Dr George Paasi (georgepaasi8@gmail.com). Mbale clinical research institute. Uganda.

Review affiliation

1. Makerere University, college of Health sciences, School of medicine, Department of Paediatric and Child Health.

Funding source

Review has no specific/external funding but is supported by guarantor/review team (non-commercial) institutions.

Peer review

There has been no peer review of this planned review.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Additional information

This systematic review is part of a doctoral research programme focused on genetic epidemiology and malaria syndemics in Africa. The protocol aligns with current global efforts to map the distribution and interplay of host genetic factors that confer resistance or susceptibility to malaria. In particular, the review addresses an evidence gap concerning epistatic interactions between multiple malaria-protective red blood cell polymorphisms, which has important implications for genetic counseling, clinical management, and precision public health in endemic regions. The findings may also support future genome-wide association studies and inform population genetic models.

Review conflict of interest

Declared individual interests are recorded under team member details.. No additional interests are recorded for this review.

Medical Subject Headings

Malaria; Erythrocyte Membrane; Genetic Predisposition to Disease; Glucosephosphate Dehydrogenase Deficiency; alpha-Thalassemia; Epistasis, Genetic; Polymorphism, Genetic;

Sickle Cell Trait; Africa South of the Sahara; Systematic Reviews as Topic

SIMILAR REVIEWS

Check for similar records already in PROSPERO

A preliminary scoping search was conducted using keywords related to epistatic interactions among malaria-protective polymorphisms and did not identify any ongoing or completed PROSPERO records addressing this specific question. Therefore, we are confident that this review addresses a novel research gap.

PROSPERO version history

- [Version 1.0, published 07 Jul 2025](#)

Disclaimer

The content of this record displays the information provided by the review team. PROSPERO does not peer review registration records or endorse their content.

PROSPERO accepts and posts the information provided in good faith; responsibility for record content rests with the review team. The guarantor for this record has affirmed that the information provided is truthful and that they understand that deliberate provision of inaccurate information may be construed as scientific misconduct.

PROSPERO does not accept any liability for the content provided in this record or for its use. Readers use the information provided in this record at their own risk.

Any enquiries about the record should be referred to the named review contact